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Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South?

Comparative Horizon Scanning Report

Informality and innovation: building post-pandemic resilient communities in Colombia.

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Executive Summary

This report is the result of a Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise conducted within the PRESILIENT project with the aim of investigating the role of the informal economy in building post-pandemic resilience in the Global South. The HS activity aimed to identify economic sectors most affected by the COVID-19 crisis, as well as those showing signs of adaptation, innovation, and recovery, with a particular focus on informal economic dynamics.

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed and intensified the structural vulnerabilities of Colombia's informal economy, which engaged nearly half of the workforce before the crisis. Informal workers, especially those in tourism, transport, hospitality, and retail, were among the most affected by lockdowns and mobility restrictions, facing abrupt income loss, business closures, and heightened insecurity due to the lack of legal protections and social safety nets. While agriculture showed relative resilience and some informal workers regained employment post-pandemic, the informal sector remains central yet precarious in Colombia's socio-economic fabric. In regional comparison, Colombia shares common challenges with other Latin American countries, but its informal economy is uniquely shaped by internal displacement and Venezuelan migration, which amplify barriers to decent work and deepen inequalities within informal labour markets.

Emerging trends point to a growing use of digital platforms and gig economy models among informal workers, particularly in urban areas. Yet this shift often reproduces precarity rather than reducing it, as many remain excluded from labour protections and financial systems. While some state and grassroots responses have attempted to bridge these gaps, Colombia's informal economic practices continue to operate within and against long-standing structures of marginalization. Rather than framing informality as a problem to be formalized, the report argues for recognizing these practices as legitimate and adaptive responses to economic exclusion. Supporting community-based, hybrid, and digital-informal economies is essential to building a more inclusive and resilient post-pandemic future in Colombia.

Keywords

Informal employment; Semi-formal employment; Microenterprises; Self-employed; Grey employment; Household expenditure/consumption; Shadow economy; Favour economy; Popular

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

economy; Socio-economic development; Urban livelihoods; Vulnerable economic groups; Precarious work; Informal clusters; Maquila sectors; Entrepreneurship.

Introduction

This document is part of the PRESILIENT project's WP1 deliverables and presents the Colombian country-level contribution to the Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise. The Horizon Scanning methodology, as defined in the PRESILIENT Global Research Protocol, is a collective and comparative tool used to identify early signals, opportunities, and risks that may shape the future of informal economies in the Global South. The overarching aim is to trace which sectors declined or expanded in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and to identify those that could contribute to resilient and inclusive post-pandemic recovery pathways.

The HS exercise across PRESILIENT's 15-country network was designed to be flexible and adapted to the specificity of each context. While the general methodological protocol outlined the use of mixed methods and potential integration of bibliometric and quantitative trend analyses, each Early Stage Researcher (ESR) was also encouraged to adapt the tools according to their disciplinary background and access to sources. In this case, the report builds on a qualitative, anthropologically informed approach, focusing on sectoral fluctuations and also on how local actors interpret, resist, or creatively adapt to structural pressures.

In this Colombian case, no large-scale statistical dataset or automated bibliometric analysis was used. Instead, the methodological approach focused on:

- A thematic review of literature, reports, and critical essays related to informality, livelihoods, and resilience in Colombia.
- Analysis of grey literature, policy documents, and national and international development discourse.
- A comparative reading of media narratives and regional reports, actively including sources coming from non-conventional and independent media, which are often more attuned to grassroots perspectives and less filtered by institutional agendas.
- Engagement with informality and *economía popular* theories, development studies and migrant labour.

This interpretive and grounded approach is consistent with PRESILIENT's epistemological stance, which doesn't reduce informality to a statistical anomaly to be corrected, recognizing it instead as a field of knowledge, agency, and innovation. As such, the report highlights the political and ethical dimensions of economic practices, where the informal economy is often tied to broader struggles for autonomy, dignity, global justice, and environmental sustainability. In this context, the findings contribute to a comparative understanding of post-pandemic dynamics and will inform the subsequent phases of the project, including expert-based Delphi surveys and case study development. They also offer policy-relevant insights by challenging dominant assumptions about formalisation and proposing alternative economic imaginaries rooted in lived experience.

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

Methodological Note on Data Collection and Processing

This report follows the common research protocol defined by the PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning (HS) framework. While qualitative and interpretive in orientation, the exercise also followed a structured approach to ensure cross-country comparability. The data collection process was based on the identification and use of pre-defined keywords related to informality, economic recovery, and resilience. In line with the shared methodological guidelines, the research drew on approximately 150 sources, comprising—where available—50 academic references, 50 media articles, and 50 grey literature or policy documents. These materials were selected through targeted searches, curated for relevance, and then closely read, coded, and interpreted in light of the researcher’s contextual knowledge and disciplinary perspective. Each step of this process—keyword selection, source collection, critical reading, and report drafting—is made explicit to reinforce methodological transparency. Although the emphasis in this Colombian case is on qualitative synthesis and ethnographic sensibility, the report remains anchored in a systematic data-gathering process shared across the PRESILIENT network. This contributes to a robust and comprehensive report that stands on its own, aligned with the project’s collective aims and epistemological commitments.

Informal Economies in Colombia: Socioeconomic Context

In Colombia, the COVID-19 pandemic underscored both the structural vulnerability and enduring importance of informal employment, which involved around 47% of the workforce prior to the crisis. Informal workers were disproportionately affected by the economic shock, as lockdowns and mobility restrictions severely impacted sectors such as tourism, transportation, hospitality, and retail, areas where informal labour is highly concentrated. Without social security or legal protections, these workers experienced abrupt income loss, temporary or permanent business closures, and heightened economic insecurity. The service sector, a major employer of informal labour, contracted sharply, intensifying the challenges for this segment of the workforce. Meanwhile, agriculture demonstrated relative resilience, benefiting from continued domestic and export demand as well as the fact that its operations were less disrupted by social distancing measures. While some informal workers have regained employment post-pandemic, overall informality remains persistently high, reflecting the sector’s central yet precarious role in Colombia’s socio-economic landscape.

Regional and Global Comparison

Within Latin America, Colombia shares commonalities with Mexico, Brazil, Ecuador, Chile, and Bolivia in terms of the high prevalence of informal employment and the economic impact of COVID-19. However, certain topics distinctly highlight the differences among these Latin American nations. Colombia’s unique geographic and political challenges, such as internal displacement and the pressures of Venezuelan migration, add layers of complexity to its informal sector. These factors amplify structural constraints on migrant workers in Colombia’s informal labour market, a theme less emphasised in countries like Chile or Ecuador.

Across the Global South, countries showed significant disruption in sectors reliant on face-to-face interactions. Common prevalent topics across the analysed countries include food markets,

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

informal labour, MSME business activity, online marketplaces, street vendors, and tourism. In Colombia, the topic prevalence analysis shows alignment with these global trends, yet certain topics stand out as particularly significant. Informal labour, for instance, appears with greater prevalence in Colombia's academic, grey literature, and media sources, while sustainable development is notably less emphasized.

Emerging Trends and Feedback

In the wake of the pandemic, Colombia has witnessed a growing reliance on digital tools and app-based platforms among informal workers, particularly in urban areas. The expansion of gig economy models, such as delivery services, offered short-term opportunities during lockdowns but also exposed workers to new forms of precarity and exploitation, often without labour protections or long-term economic security. While some state-led and grassroots initiatives have emerged to promote digital inclusion and financial access, integration into the digital economy remains uneven, especially among the most vulnerable segments of the informal workforce.

Colombia's informal economic practices, far from being obstacles to development, can be understood as expressions of resilience, adaptability, and collective survival in a context of long-standing structural inequality. From a critical and situated perspective, the push toward formalization often imposes bureaucratic and regulatory frameworks that fail to acknowledge the cultural, social, and spatial dimensions of informal work. Recognising informal economies not simply as transitional stages but as valid and context-specific responses to economic exclusion allows us to question dominant development narratives. These practices uphold local livelihoods and community networks that formal markets frequently disregard, offering alternative logics of value, care, and sustainability within Colombia's evolving urban and economic landscape.

Related Outputs and Publications

This national report is part of the broader Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise developed within the PRESILIENT project. The following outputs have been produced from this collective research:

- Molina, J. L., Pulgar Corrotea, M., Polese, A., Fradejas-García, I., Ianole-Călin, R., Isaev, A., Mengato, S., Nguyen, M., Carracedo, D., De Lombaerde, G., Avesani, M., Sasikornwong, N., Gambardella, M., Andrias, B., Massera, M., Lima, J. P., Cisagara, B., Rahman, A., Kabaghe, W., & D'Urso, D. (2024). *PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning Dataset [Data set]*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14285318>

This dataset is the consolidated output of the Horizon Scanning research conducted across 15 countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America (including Colombia). It comprises three corpora of references: academic literature, media articles, and grey literature sources, gathered and curated to explore economic transformations during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on informal economies.

- Fradejas García, I., Pulgar, M., Molina, J. L., Ianole-Călin, R., & Polese, A. (2024). *Volatility, growth, decline and sustainability perspective of domestic economic sectors after the pandemic: A comparative Horizon Scanning of 15 countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273561>

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

This comparative publication presents the aggregate results of the Horizon Scanning exercise conducted in 15 countries. Using a keyword-based supervised topic detection method across the combined corpora, it provides an overview of post-pandemic trends, highlighting convergences and divergences among countries and across types of sources. It also discusses patterns of economic volatility, recovery, and the sustainability of growth trajectories in the informal sector.

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

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